

NFDI4Earth

Milestone MS1.3.3

**Initial set of modular
NFDI4Earth-ready course materials
published under an open license**

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2023-06 | Version: 1

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10353072](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10353072)

nfdi4earth.de

Citation

Farzaneh Sadeghi, Casten Keßler. 2023. *Initial set of modular NFDI4Earth-ready course materials published under an open license (NFDI4Earth Milestone MS1.3.3) (NFDI4Earth Deliverable MS1.3.3)*. NFDI4Earth Community on Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10353072>

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Acknowledgement

This work has been funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) through the project NFDI4Earth (DFG project no. 460036893, <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/>) within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, <https://www.nfdi.de/>).

Executive summary

This report details the progress and plans for Measure 1.3 of the NFDI4Earth, aimed at developing and publishing course materials and curricula. These resources are and will be designed to cover the use of NFDI4Earth services and principles in Research Data Management (RDM) and Earth System Data Science (ESDS). The initial set of NFDI4Earth-ready course materials has been published under an open license, leveraging the Open edX Tutor Instance. The Open edX-based NFDI4Earth educational portal houses content developed by the EduTrain team as well as materials from the first round of NFDI4Earth educational pilots. A content library is also under development to streamline course creation and maintain consistency across courses. Two courses, namely “Image Processing and Analysis” and “How to create publishable NetCDF-data”, have been published and made accessible to the public, with more in the pipeline. A cornerstone of the project is the adoption of open licenses, particularly the Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license, for all course modules. This licensing strategy ensures the widest possible dissemination and use of educational resources. Challenges encountered during the project are systematically recorded and addressed in the EduTrain project within the NFDI4Earth GitLab. The report concludes with the project’s future direction, which includes enhancing platform interactivity, expanding the course catalogue, refining the curriculum, and continuously improving the learner experience.

Abbreviations

NFDI - National Research Data Infrastructure

NFDI4Earth - National Research Data Infrastructure for Earth System Science

RDM - Research Data Management

ESDS - Earth System Data Science

LMS - Learning Management System

OERs - Open Educational Resources

CC0 - Creative Commons Zero

CC - Creative Commons

MOOC - Massive Open Online Course

OS4A - One Stop 4 All

KH - Knowledge Hub

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1 Introduction

Measure 1.3 aims to develop and publish NFDI4Earth-ready course materials and curricula under an open license. These modules are designed to be integrated into existing university curricula or function as independent stand-alone courses. The overall objective is to cover the usage of NFDI4Earth services and the application of NFDI4Earth principles in RDM, and ESDS.

This report delves into the details of M1.3.3, “the initial set of modular NFDI4Earth-ready course materials published under an open license”. Leveraging the Open edX Tutor Instance, a flexible, scalable, and feature-rich learning management system (LMS), our team has published the initial set of modules. This report details the various components of this milestone achievement, presenting insights into the Open edX platform, module development, interactivity, curriculum development, and the future roadmap.

2 NFDI4Earth educational portal

In the quest for a platform to serve as the foundation of the NFDI4Earth educational portal, we evaluated numerous options based on criteria such as flexibility, scalability, support, and security (see [D1.3.12](#)). Open edX [1], an open-source learning management system was selected due to its wide range of features, flexibility, scalability, and extensive support community.

The first round of published materials includes content developed by the EduTrain team and content from the first round of NFDI4Earth educational pilots.

2.1 Open edX

Open edX Tutor Instance is a Docker-based Open edX distribution, which simplifies the deployment, customisation, and upgrades of the platform. It offers several benefits, such as reduced time for setting up, easier maintenance, and enhanced reliability. It also supports various plugins to extend functionality [2].

The Open edX Studio is a great tool for course developers to create and manage interactive content in a user-friendly environment. With its drag-and-drop interfaces, built-in templates for course structures, and integration with various multimedia tools, The Studio makes it easy to deliver rich content to students. It also allows for managing course schedules and monitoring student progress. Thanks to its robust features like video lectures, quizzes, discussion forums, peer-to-peer social learning, and machine-graded and peer-graded assignments, the Studio has been adopted by educational institutions and organisations worldwide (see Fig. 1).

The LMS of Open edX is the interface that learners interact with. It has been designed for a smooth and intuitive user experience. Open edX serves as the foundation of our course

Figure 1: Open edX studio

delivery. Its flexibility allows for comprehensive course design, including various interactive elements. The overall theme of the LMS will be based on NFDI4Earth mock-ups for One Stop 4 All (OS4A). The design of further details such as course images ensures a maintainable system for future updates. This minimal and maintainable design enhances navigability and coherence throughout the Educational portal and the whole OS4A and ensures easy updating as the project evolves (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Open edX LMS

A straightforward guide for navigating and utilising Open edX Studio in line with the N4E goals is currently under development. This will be instrumental in ensuring courses are created in a way

that enables learners to fully engage with the resources and activities within the courses. All the courses from our LMS will be harvested automatically into the Knowledge Hub (KH), making it easy for learners and educators to find, use, and share our resources (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Working with NFDI4Earth educational portal

To streamline course creation and maintain consistency across courses, a content library is being developed. It will house common elements such as feedback surveys and default course homepages. This shared resource will foster consistency across courses and expedite the course creation process.

2.2 Publishing modules

We began our educational offerings with a suite of courses focused on spatial data analysis using Python. These range from an introductory course that lays the foundation for more advanced topics such as courses on image processing techniques and machine learning. Our curriculum is enhanced by original materials, designed by our educational pilots, or used in our educational events. These resources are available to all learners seeking to expand their technical capabilities in this field.

To provide a comprehensive learning experience, we have integrated a range of established libraries into our courses. These include key libraries such as Pandas, Matplotlib, OpenCV, and sklearn, which play a central role in data analysis and machine learning. Furthermore, we support specialised spatial data analysis through geopandas and rasterio, among others. By incorporating these libraries, we aim to equip learners with the essential skills needed to address real-world challenges in their respective fields.

We are committed to improving and broadening our curriculum. Currently, we are working on creating new courses and refining existing ones to cover a wider range of topics and skills. Our goal is to ensure that our community has access to the most comprehensive and current learning resources.

Open licensing is a critical factor in facilitating the use of Open Educational Resources (OERs). By

adopting the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license model, we ensure that our course materials are widely accessible and adaptable [3]. This licensing model provides preemptive permission grants, thus eliminating the need for individuals to seek permission each time they want to use or modify the materials. Various open licenses can be used with OERs, with Creative Commons being the most commonly utilised. Creative Commons offers a suite of free licenses, ranging from the most liberal, CC0, which waives all rights and places the work in the public domain, to the most restrictive, CC BY-NC-ND, which permits others to use the work but not adapt it or use it for commercial purposes [4].

We have picked the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license as our default for all course modules. This ensures broad accessibility and allows others to use, adapt, and distribute these resources freely while giving credit to the original authors [3], which is a common courtesy and a best practice. While the CC BY license is our primary choice, we understand that certain situations might necessitate a different Creative Commons license. For instance, if a course incorporates third-party materials that prohibit commercial use, or if there are other specific requirements, we are flexible in adjusting our licensing choices. Such adaptability ensures that our licenses align with the unique needs and contexts of each educational resource we provide.

To maximise the reach and impact of our courses, we intend to distribute our courses through major MOOC and OER providers, leveraging their established platforms to reach a wider global audience. These distribution strategies, in combination with our open licensing, are intended to make our courses as widely accessible as possible, facilitating the broad dissemination of skills and knowledge in Earth System Data Science.

2.3 Courses and modules overview

This section provides an overview of our current course offerings, some of which are still in the pre-publication phase [5]. For detailed information on each module, please visit our educational portal: <https://nfdi4earth-edutrain.geo.tu-dresden.de/>.

2.3.1 Course: Python Onboarding

Course Curriculum:

- Installation and Practical Considerations
- How to Run Python Code
- Python Language Syntax
- Basic Python Semantics: Variables and Objects
- Built-In Types: Simple Values
- Basic Python Semantics: Operators

- Built-In Data Structures
- Defining and Using Functions and Classes
- Control Flow
- Errors and Exceptions
- Iterators
- List Comprehensions
- Generators
- Modules and Packages
- Strings and Regular Expressions
- A Preview of Data Science Tools

2.3.2 Course: Python for Spatial Data Analysis

Course Curriculum:

- Intro to GIScience and Data Analysis
- Basics of Python
- Exploratory Data Analysis
- Vector-based Spatial Analysis
- Advanced Spatial Analysis with PySAL
- Raster-based Spatial Analysis
- Terrain Analysis
- Spatial Interpolation: A Quick Tour
- Remote Sensing Image Analysis in Python
- Google Earth Engine
- Interactive Maps
- LIDAR Data Visualization

2.3.3 Module: Image Processing and Analysis

Module Courses:

- Basic Image Processing: Load and Show, Spilt the channel of colour image, Invert the colour, Mean value and variance value, Histogram
- Image filters: Basic convolution operation, Image smoothing with Box Filter and Binomial Filter and Median Filter, Image gradient with Sobel Filter, Laplacian filter
- Morphology and image thresholding: Morphology, Image thresholding, Example of simple road extraction

- Extraction of regions and edges: Region Growing, Watershed Transformation, Mean Shift Segmentation, SLIC superpixels algorithm, Douglas Peucker Algorithm, Hough transformation
- Geometric Transformations of Images: Scaling, Affine Transformation, Translation, Rotation, Arbitrary affine transform, Perspective Transformation
- Harris Corner Detection: Sobel Operator, Structure Matrix, Corner response function

2.3.4 Module: Machine Learning

Module Courses:

- Linear and Polynomial Regressions with sklearn: LinearRegression Model, Train_test_split Method, Cross_val_score
- Logistic Regression with sklearn: Train_test_split Method, Logistic_regression Model, Confusion_matrix
- Clustering and Classification with sklearn, pandas, and matplotlib: KMeans Model, K-Means Algorithm, K-Medoids and DBSCAN Models
- Machine Learning Classifier

2.3.5 Course: How to Create Publishable NetCDF-Data

Course Curriculum:

- The NetCDF Data Format
- CF Conventions
- Essential Metadata in the NetCDF Header
- Creating CF Compliant NetCDF Files
- Special Formats in NetCDF: Single Insitu Measurements, Ship Observations, Profiles, etc.

2.3.6 Course: Understanding Data Chunking

Course Curriculum:

- Loading Different Chunks and Their Properties
- Global Per-pixel Statistics and Time Steps
- Performance of Data Processing Across Different Chunks
- The Relevance of Chunking During Data Processing

3 Challenges

The “EduTrain” project within NFDI4Earth GitLab is used to record challenges and problems and improve possibilities as issues. By using GitLab’s issue tracking, we benefit from a centralised system where all team members can easily view, comment on, and contribute to resolving issues. It also enables us to categorise and prioritise issues, track their progress, and document their resolutions, supplying a history of problem-solving efforts and decisions. The EduTrain team together with the software developer team researched solutions to the recorded issues. One of the key obstacles we encounter is that the Open edX platform lacks built-in support for interactive notebooks. To overcome this limitation and to enhance the practicality and immersion of our courses, we have added a MyBinder button [6]. This button enables users to open and run Jupyter Notebooks directly from our GitLab repository in an interactive environment without any setup. It facilitates a seamless transition between learning and hands-on coding, which is especially beneficial for those who are new to programming or those who have not set up a local Python environment.

Although MyBinder is an important tool in education, we acknowledge the importance of having Google Colab as a backup. Google Colab is well-known for its strong infrastructure and widespread use, which can be crucial for notebooks with high computational demand [7]. By keeping Google Colab as an option, learners can have a consistent experience even if they run into unexpected issues with MyBinder. Furthermore, we make all our courses accessible on GitLab, facilitating their download and reuse by the broader community (Fig. 2) [8].

It is important to mention that the integration with Google Colab is not a permanent solution. We are currently researching open-source options or looking to develop our own in-house solutions that better align with our policies.

Moreover, to enrich the learning experience, we are exploring innovative ways to incorporate more interactivity into the platform, such as integrating third-party tools, developing in-house applications, and using Open edX’s extensive plugin ecosystem.

4 Conclusion and future direction

Having achieved this milestone, the NFDI4Earth project is geared towards enhancing interactivity on the platform, expanding the course catalogue, refining the curriculum, and continuously improving the learner experience. This includes the continuous analysis and adaptation of course materials, regular educational events, and the establishment of an open network of NFDI4Earth EduHubs offering long-term educational services.

Parallel to the course module development, we are working on a comprehensive curriculum that will integrate these modules into a larger learning structure. The goal is to build larger

modules out of these micro-modules, creating an encompassing learning experience for our stakeholders.

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